

Activating Fab Labs for Classroom Learning: Supporting K-12 teachers in technology integration

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Abstract

In response to the maker movement, administrators are adding 3D printers, laser cutters, vinyl cutters, and other computer-controlled machinery into school-based makerspaces at a rapid rate. These digital fabrication tools can potentially engage students in hands-on learning across all subject areas. However, adding these extra tools into schools doesn't always lead to the adoption of these digital fabrication tools into the school curriculum. New technologies are often used as novelty experiences or elective-based, stand-alone maker classes. Still, the tools themselves can catalyze innovative learning if integrated into subjects outside of the isolated "technology" or "STEAM" courses. In this improvement science study, four teachers participated in an intervention centering the TPACK framework of teacher knowledge, which included virtual working sessions to develop lesson plans integrating these tools into classroom learning. Participants reported increased confidence with the tools. However, there were mixed levels of confidence in using these tools *with students*. Attention to embedded practice, professional learning communities, and technology integration and pedagogy knowledge show promise for supporting teachers new to this technology toolset.

Keywords

Education, digital fabrication, teacher training

1 The Promise of School-Based Fab Labs

The maker movement has garnered widespread attention in recent years, significantly impacting society through events like Maker Faires, DIY channels on platforms such as YouTube. This movement has also seen a surge in youth participation, with millions identifying themselves as makers through both physical gatherings and online platforms. Concurrently, the cost of rapid prototyping technologies has steadily decreased, making tools like 3D printers and other computer-controlled machinery more accessible to a broader range of individuals and institutions.

Taking advantage of this momentum and affordability, K12 schools are increasingly integrating makerspaces into their educational environments. These spaces, equipped with resources such as 3D printers and laser cutters, are being incorporated into classrooms, libraries, and other communal areas within school buildings (Bull et al., 2014; Chan & Blikstein, 2018; Martin, 2015; Song, 2018). This expansion holds promise for transforming classroom dynamics, offering opportunities for constructionist learning through iterative, collaborative projects that empower students (Blikstein et al., 2017; Harmer et al., 2021). As these makerspaces adopt computer-controlled machinery, the potential for hands-on, digital making to enhance student learning experiences continues to grow.

1.1 The Origins of Educational Making

Many theorists attribute the foundational principles of student-centered learning in makerspaces to Seymour Papert, often regarded as the pioneer of the maker movement (Peterson & Scharber, 2018; Fab Foundation, 2019). Papert's constructionist learning theory proposes that children construct their own models of knowledge through building and sharing projects. He expanded on Jean Piaget's constructivist theory by introducing physical artifacts and mental models as important aspects to learning (Papert, 1980, pp. vi-vii; Piaget, 1970). This view of constructionism forms the basis for modern maker education, where students create learning artifacts using various methods from cardboard and scissors to laser cutters. This approach aligns with Papert's vision of learning through active creation, underscoring the educational value of hands-on making in both physical and digital realms.

Fab Labs and digital makerspaces in schools can provide constructivist opportunities for students to engage in the iterative design process (through prototyping and iterating) to create physical artifacts that reflect content learning and personal connections (Petrich et al., 2013; Quinn & Bell, 2013); Rayna & Striukova, 2021). The method and process of artifact-making can support content learning outcomes in any subject matter and provide an opportunity to develop STEM student competencies like creativity, problem-solving, collaboration, and artistic expression (PA Department of Education, 2020; Valtonen, 2020). In addition, the computer-aided design process, with its emphasis on modeling and visualization, provides an opportunity for more profound student learning in other content areas (Eisenberg & Buechley, 2008; Bull et al., 2014; Bevan, 2017). Through modeling and prototype design, students can explore the content while engaging their STEM competencies deeply. However, this authentic integration of these technologies is not common; instead, these tools are often used as a novelty activity or a one-time experience with technology (Brown, 2015; Cairns et al., 2018). For instance, 3D printing activities in the classroom often consist of students downloading a predesigned shape (cartoon characters are popular) and then watching as the printer slowly extrudes the shape onto the printing platform layer by layer. While this activity excites new learners about the technology, it does not integrate content or activate deeper learning and personal connection with the subject area.

In addition to isolating digital making into one-time novelty experiences for children, educators exploring the technology more deeply with their students tend to exaggerate the focus on students learning about the technology rather than learning with or through the technology (Brennan, 2015, p. 289). Schools will often silo the digital makerspace rooms for specific elective courses like maker classes or STEAM classes where the curriculum tends to focus on using the technology with little connection to learning outcomes from other content areas.

Though rapidly appearing in classrooms across the United States, digital fabrication tools and technologies are often not used to enhance student learning through the curriculum.

More profound classroom use of digital fabrication technologies depends on teacher preparation to integrate these tools (Milara et al., 2020). However, schools are adding digital makerspaces at a fast pace, often without proper training for the educators working in these makerspaces (Lassiter et al., 2013; Oliver, 2016; Valtonen, 2020). Teacher training and preparation programs lag behind the sudden adoption of new digital makerspace technologies; therefore, teachers are not prepared to use these tools effectively.

1.2 The Perspective of the Teacher

As both a practitioner and researcher, I collaborate with schools and school districts to develop and integrate digital makerspaces into their buildings and curricula, often conducting teacher trainings alongside my consultation work (eduFAB, 2024). To address the widespread issue of digital makerspaces being underutilized in schools, I conducted sixteen empathy interviews with in-service teachers. A clear pattern emerged from these interviews: educators were struggling to effectively use digital fabrication tools to support student learning in the classroom.

After conducting empathy interviews with teachers, I categorized them into two distinct groups based on their classroom learning objectives: one focused on technology and engineering classes, emphasizing tools and processes, while the other remained within their content areas, adhering to subject-specific curricula.

Technology Teachers focus on teaching about technology with learning objectives centered around the tools themselves. These educators often develop their own curricula to instruct students on the safe use of digital and non-digital fabrication technologies and building projects with the toolset.

In contrast, Subject Area Teachers, covering subjects like English, history, and biology, have learning objectives driven by standards, assessments, and curriculum rather than technology. They often lack training in digital fabrication tools and are unaware of integration opportunities.

1.3 Problem Statement

Based on my practical experience, along with multiple empathy interviews with teachers and two semi-structured interviews with administrators, I created an Ishikawa diagram to highlight the challenges contributing to the underutilization of digital makerspaces in education (Milosavljevic et al., 2020). This diagram, Figure 1, resembles a fish skeleton and visualizes the problem's contributing factors as the "bones." The contributing problem areas include time and space, technology knowledge, pedagogy and integration knowledge, support network, and standardized testing. The problem statement forms the "head" of the skeleton, "Teachers are not sufficiently supported to integrate digital fabrication technologies in their classrooms for student learning."

Figure 1: Ishikawa Diagram

Note. Visualization of the problem in the context of contributing factors, or "bones." Own work.

2 Contextualizing Digital Fabrication in Education

While digital fabrication makerspaces in schools are relatively new to formal education, there is a growing body of literature addressing this topic. My research specifically focuses on digital fabrication tools and technologies within this context, distinct from the broader literature on "making," "makerspaces," and "maker education," which are more extensively studied. I use the term "digital makerspace" to refer to a makerspace equipped with tools such as 3D printers, laser cutters, vinyl cutters, CNC mills, and electronics and programming kits (Mersand, 2021). The terms digital makerspace and Fab Lab are used

interchangeably throughout this study, since Fab Labs all incorporate digital making technologies (Fab Foundation, 2019; Nemorin, 2017).

To approach the literature addressing the challenge of underutilized digital makerspaces in schools, I isolated two research questions to consider:

- How are these technologies currently being used in the formal classroom?
- How do teachers best learn to integrate new technologies?

2.1 Digital Fabrication Tools in Schools

Research has revealed that there are a variety of theories and practices for using digital fabrication in the classroom. However, there is no agreed-upon strategy for integrating these tools into formal education, and implementation of Fab Labs and other digital makerspaces varies significantly across formal education. It is noteworthy, though, that the toolset's potential to support student-centered constructionist learning is prevalent in much of the research.

Emerging themes noted by both theorists and researchers encompass the enhancement of technological literacy, Project-Based Learning (PBL), and STEM content knowledge through the use of these tools. However, literature on integrating these tools into curriculum-based classroom learning, beyond STEM content, remains insufficiently explored.

Technological Literacy

Some researchers argue that integrating digital fabrication tools in makerspaces enhances students' technological literacy and fosters an understanding of the inner workings of tools and technologies (Martin, 2015). By using and learning about computer-controlled machines, students gain the understanding that technology is not a black box. This knowledge enhances their confidence and helps them identify as makers rather than just consumers of technology.

Kafai and Peppler (2018) expand on this concept, referring to student understanding of technology as "technological transparency" which is seen in students learning about the technology by making projects. Blikstein et al. (2017) built a tool to measure the technological learning afforded by engaging with these tools called the "Exploration and Fabrication Technologies (EFT) Instrument." This assessment distinguishes between computer literacy and digital fabrication literacy, focusing on specific skills and literacies associated with these technologies. While Blikstein et al. (2017) highlight the benefits of enhancing student confidence and performance with digital fabrication technologies, they also caution against technocentrism—the overemphasis on technical objects rather than the deeper understanding they can facilitate. Papert (1987) similarly warned against technocentrism in educational programming, advocating instead for technology to foster understanding.

Enhancement to Problem-Based-Learning

Building on Papert's constructionist theory, many researchers advocate for problem-based learning (PBL) in educational makerspaces, emphasizing the creation of personal artifacts to demonstrate learning (Brennan, 2015; Bull et al., 2010; Cairns et al., 2018; Chan & Blikstein, 2018; Doppelt, 2003; Smith, 2018). PBL shifts the focus from teacher-led lessons to student-driven exploration, where students define learning objectives based on real-world scenarios and engage in self-directed learning, often collaborating in groups to propose solutions (Awang & Ramly, 2008).

PBL units integrate content across subject areas, and since makerspaces naturally foster interdisciplinary activities, combining these tools with such projects holds significant promise (Vuorikari et al., 2019). Kolmos (1996) initially proposed project work within problem-oriented, project-based learning (PBL), which later evolved into design-based learning (DBL). DBL emphasizes the creation of a learning artifact within a PBL framework (Doppelt, 2008; Puente et al., 2011).

Doppelt (2008) and his team further developed DBL, where students engage in hands-on activities to construct cognitive concepts through inventive and creative projects that they make to demonstrate learning. They studied both high achieving and low achieving students increased understanding through the use of DBL in their units. While these studies did not specifically focus on digital fabrication tools or computer-aided design (CAD), they underscored the importance of students creating artifacts within a PBL framework. Integrating digital fabrication tools could potentially enhance this process of artifact creation.

In a study focusing on CAD within DBL, Smith (2018) observed improved visualization skills among younger students participating in a summer program. This program combined digital and analog design processes, demonstrating the effectiveness of DBL in fostering student learning despite the exact causal link between CAD and skill improvement remaining unclear.

In 2018, Blikstein and Chan collaborated on a study with middle school students and educators exploring the intersection of PBL with digital fabrication tools. Unlike previous studies by Doppelt and Smith, this study did not measure specific subject-area learning outcomes but aimed to understand student collaboration and teacher interactions in this context. Chan and Blikstein found that PBL with digital fabrication tools fostered student-driven learning and transformed traditional student-teacher dynamics (Chan & Blikstein, 2018). While the study highlighted increased collaboration and student-centered learning, the researchers acknowledged that attributing these outcomes solely to the tools was challenging. They emphasized the need for further research to explore the synergies between PBL and digital fabrication tools more comprehensively.

Engaging STEM Content Through Design

Another emerging theme in the use of digital fabrication tools in classrooms revolves around the design phase of making, specifically design with computers or computer-aided-design (CAD). Unlike PBL, some research focuses on integrating digital fabrication with specific design prompts, or "project work" as termed by Kolmos (1996). This approach involves students addressing a particular design challenge developed by the teacher rather than solving an open-ended real-world problem, potentially enhancing STEM content learning through CAD (Bull et al., 2014; Nemorin, 2017). While this method does not achieve the student-driven learning and design potential seen in DBL studies still show promise for deepening STEM content understanding with the digital fabrication toolset.

The design aspect of digital fabrication is highly effective for learning STEM content. Bevan (2017) introduced the term "STEM-Rich Making," which emphasizes deep engagement with scientific and mathematical concepts through iterative design and digital tools. Eisenberg & Buechley (2008) also noted that creating real-world objects from computer models enhances learning, as students can interact with their physical designs. This CAD process, combined with physical modeling, offers a unique opportunity for students to learn STEM content both virtually and physically. Other researchers show promise for students learning content deeply through the CAD modeling phase (Hmelo et al., 2000; Burghardt et al., 2010).

Though design-focused project work is not fully integrated PBL, it is effective for STEM education. Brennan (2015) suggested that design challenges activate STEM content and encourage persistence. Other researchers also highlight the positive competencies students develop through design work, even without real-world problems (Eisenberg & Buechley, 2008; Kafai & Resnick, 1996).

2.2 Teacher Knowledge Engaged in Technology Integration

In 1986, Shulman introduced the concept of Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), emphasizing that effective teaching requires both content knowledge and pedagogical knowledge. He argued that the intersection of these two knowledge types is crucial (Shulman, 1986). Later, Mishra and Koehler (2007) expanded Shulman's PCK framework by adding a third category: technological knowledge, necessary for integrating technology into teaching. This expanded framework, known as Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge (TPACK), is shown in Figure 2 and combines content, pedagogical, and technological

knowledge to support effective teaching with technology (Koehler & Mishra, 2007; Khrine, Afari, & Ali, 2019).

Figure 2. TPACK Framework

Note. This Venn diagram shows the intersection of TPACK domains, developed by Koehler & Mishra (2007).

Though this framework originated around the technology of computers and software, researchers Koehler and Mishra (2007) openly defined technology so that it can include the tools and processes of digital fabrication. TPACK is a theory of the interconnectedness and overlap of teachers' knowledge domains in working with technology to teach in the classroom.

Many researchers indicate that teacher development programs, in general, do not provide pedagogical strategies for teachers to use technology effectively in the classroom (Koehler & Mishra, 2005; Milara et al., 2020; Pamuk, 2012; Pitkänen et al., 2019; Song, 2008). Greater focus is required to help teachers engage all areas and intersections of the TPACK framework.

Attention to Technical Knowledge

Teacher training programs often prioritize technological learning over pedagogical considerations without addressing all components of the TPACK framework for effective technology integration in education (Milara et al., 2020; Pamuk, 2012; Song, 2018).

Conversely, Brown (2015) supported a technocentric approach to teacher training for 3D printing. She argued that 3D printing involves many challenging processes, including modeling, slicing designs, preparing and maintaining the printer, and printing, so more focus is needed on the technology only.

Deeper Learning Through Connections

Connecting the three categories of teacher knowledge is essential when integrating digital fabrication technologies, as is connecting people to other people. Teachers learn best through sustained connections with other teachers experiencing the same learning trajectory. These networks, both formal and informal, are crucial in supporting one another. Whether referred to as “professional learning communities” (Cairns et al., 2018; Oliver, 2016), “informal learning communities” (Song, 2018), “study-groups” (Hjorth et al., 2017), or simply “friends” (Peterson & Scharber, 2018), these groups play a critical role.

Brennan (2018) developed a virtual support community for teachers using Scratch programming. This online community allowed educators to network, ask and answer questions, and share stories and resources, significantly aiding successful technology integration (p. 293).

Hjorth et al. (2017) supported teachers in Denmark using digital fabrication tools through a research by design study, emphasizing peer-to-peer collaboration. This structured approach, involving study groups, received positive feedback for fostering interpersonal connections and aiding learning (p. 27).

In Oulu, a study intersecting STEAM and digital fabrication training developed a comprehensive program for in-service teachers. This program included a structured Community of Practice involving teachers and other stakeholders. The structured development of stakeholders and activities led to successes in building the CoP (Milara et al., 2020).

Whether structured or casual, learning communities are repeatedly shown in research to be vital for effective teacher training in new technologies.

Classroom and Embedded Experience

A common theme among researchers is that teachers learn to teach with technology best when they can practice themselves or observe others teaching. Hjorth et al. (2017) prioritized embedded teaching experience in their Denmark-based teacher professional development program. Without practicing their new skills, teachers report feeling unprepared to try technology with their students (Pamuk, 2012).

Cairns et al. (2018) incorporated classroom practice in their three-year teacher training program. Teachers learned to integrate 3D printing into authentic lessons, developing and implementing lessons with their students, and analyzing results in professional learning communities. This study showed increased use of digital fabrication technologies, combining embedded practice and learning communities.

3 Methods

In designing this qualitative research study, an improvement science approach (NYC Department of Education, 2018) was employed, which integrates stakeholder input, organizational context, and existing literature to define a problem space and develop a theory of improvement. To operationalize this theory, I followed Hinnant-Crawford's methodology (2020) known as Plan, Do, Study, Act (PDSA), which involves iterative testing and refinement of interventions aimed at achieving specific goals. The PDSA cycle, conducted over two phases, enabled me to collaborate individually with four teachers, providing them with training on new technologies and assisting them in integrating these tools into their classroom lesson plans.

3.1 Theory of Change

Based on stakeholder interviews and a literature review, I developed a theory of change to tackle the issue of teachers being underprepared to engage students with digital making in classroom learning. I created a driver diagram to visually represent potential improvement drivers across a system, targeting a specific

improvement aim (Perry et al., 2020). My goal is to increase the number of teachers using digital fabrication tools to support student learning. The driver diagram in Figure 3 addresses two main drivers of the theory: "Teacher Knowledge" and "School Environment."

Figure 3. Driver Diagram

Note. This diagram represents the theory of change developed for the study. Attention to the top driver of Teacher Knowledge is the focus. Own work.

This PDSA study will focus on the domain of "Teacher Knowledge," through the change ideas on the right side of the diagram. My hypothesis is that after participating in the lesson plan development sessions which attend to TPACK domains, participating teachers would feel more confident using the technology with their students in the classroom.

3.2 Inquiry Questions

The inquiry questions guide the data collection from the PDSA cycles (Hinnant-Crawford, 2020). The questions below address outcome measures:

1. To what extent will the lesson plans developed by the participants integrate technology into their subject area lesson?
2. How comfortable will the teachers feel about using these technologies with their students?
3. How does the lesson plan development process affect the participants' perception of technology relevance in their own classroom?
4. How does the lesson plan development process affect participants' likelihood of using these tools with their students?

3.3 Participants

Recruiting in-service teachers for the study was difficult, as many were overwhelmed by the abrupt shift to online education in 2020, and were reluctant to engage in another virtual commitment (Bullock et al., 2022; Wong, 2020). Having started the PDSA study with eight participating teachers, scheduling conflicts persisted, and only four teachers completed the entire cycle, each spending 4-7 hours in sessions.

Both participants in cycle one were Technology Teachers from affluent districts. Both the high school (HS) and middle school (MS) teacher taught their classes in the makerspace. They were proficient with 3D printers, laser cutters, and vinyl cutters. I refer to them as HS and MS.

Subject Area Teachers participated in cycle two;. One was a 4-6 music teacher (MT) from a Title I school and the other a K-5 librarian (KL) from an affluent school district. While one school had digital making technologies available, neither teacher had used them before in their classrooms.

3.4 Lesson Plan Development Intervention Procedure

In this improvement science study, I served as both the trainer and researcher, spending significant one-on-one time with each participant. Working independently with each teacher, I tailored my words and actions to their specific needs, adjusting the sessions based on real-time feedback and the unique requirements of each teacher. Unlike traditional researchers who primarily observe, my actions could potentially affect the outcome, so to mitigate this risk, I followed the intervention procedure Table 1, closely, separating training sessions from data collection protocols.

Table 1. Intervention Procedure

Introduction	30-60 minutes	brief introduction of myself, teacher introduction, explanation of the intervention process
Technology Training	60-120 minutes	(depending on teacher) installation of software, walk through design and making steps, practice
Ideation and Research	30-60 minutes	discuss learning goals, browse other lesson plans on SCOPES-DF website, brainstorm ideas for lesson
Lesson Development	30-90 minutes	using the SCOPES-DF lesson planning template, identify learning goals and begin work on lesson plan
Additional Development	30-60 minutes	some teachers worked additionally on their own time before presenting the lesson plan
Lesson Sharing	45-60 minutes	teachers presented or shared their lesson plan

4 Measures and Analysis

Throughout this study, I collected data through surveys, interviews, and field notes to provide a rich understanding of the link between embedded lesson design development with one-on-one support and teachers' perceptions of these technologies for use in the classroom.

Participants completed both a pre-survey and a post-survey, with the pre-survey also serving as a screening tool during recruitment. I maintained field notes throughout the working sessions. Short, semi-structured interviews were conducted with all participants post-intervention and I also collected lesson plans.

4.1 Lesson Plan Development Sessions

Each of the two Technology Teachers in the first cycle approached lesson development with attention to non-technology learning goals in addition to their usual technocentric instruction goals. Through our conversations, we drew out different goals for student learning and formed lesson ideas around those goals. In addition to technology learning goals, MS centered their lesson around practicing creativity with their students. However, HS was more interested in redesigning a lesson that would interest young girls in their technology classes.

Due to the lack of technical knowledge among the Subject Area Teachers in cycle two, I provided virtual sessions on setting up and using 12" vinyl cutters. These online sessions lasted two to three hours each. Both teachers used the vinyl cutter in their lesson plans but focused on non-technological learning goals: MT's 5th-grade music students explored graphical interpretations of band logos, and KL integrated robot programming with designing cultural graphics into her library lesson for third graders. These teachers also spent more time in sessions with me, averaging seven hours each, while cycle one participants only spent four to five hours each with me in sessions. Additionally, cycle two participants didn't participate in the lesson plan sharing session due to scheduling conflicts.

4.2 Lesson Plan Analysis

To measure outcomes, I analyzed each completed lesson plan by using the SAMR hierarchy (Puentedura, 2006). The SAMR model classifies technology integration into four levels: Substitution, Augmentation, Modification, and Redefinition, each indicating increasing levels of impact on learning tasks (Hamilton, Rosenberg, & Akcaoglu, 2016). Substitution and augmentation, being the two lowest on the hierarchy, are considered on the enhancement tier, while modification and redefinition are on the transformative tier.

In cycle one, both Technology Teachers integrated technology into their lesson plans at the "transformative" tier of the SAMR hierarchy. MS's lesson plan reached the "modification" level, where students used a vinyl cutter to decorate and label creativity journals. This level involves a significant redesign of the task, offering new options and processes compared to non-digital tasks (Hamilton et al., 2016). The lesson also taught creativity within constraints such as vinyl color and size.

HS's lesson plan ranked at the highest level of the SAMR scale, "redefinition." This comprehensive lesson plan included multiple digital fabrication technologies and was more extensive than MS's. HS's students engaged in research, design, and fabrication to build a website for a fundraising sales project. They used 3D CAD software, a 3D printer, or a laser cutter to create products for sale. At the "redefinition" level, technology enabled projects that would be impossible otherwise, including the introduction of generative design.

In cycle two, the lesson plans were not completed to the same level of detail as they were in cycle one. KL's lesson plan for their library class integrated the vinyl cutter at an augmentation level according to the SAMR scale. "At the Augmentation level, technology is exchanged, and the function of the task or tool positively changes in some way" (Hamilton et al., 2016, p.434). In this lesson plan, students researched their assigned country, designed graphical representations, cut them into stickers using a vinyl cutter, and placed the stickers on a shared world map. They then programmed robots to visit the countries. Previously, KL had students draw pictures with markers, but integrating the vinyl cutter enhanced the lesson and positively transformed the task.

For the music teacher, MT, the lesson plan was designed specifically with the vinyl cutter. The lesson uses the technology at the level of "modification" on the SAMR scale. In this lesson, students researched the logo designs of their favorite bands and considered how logos change over time to reflect the culture. Then the students recreated their band logos for cutting on the vinyl cutter, and they put their new stickers on their music notebooks. This lesson is similar in scope to the creativity lesson in cycle one and lands at the "modification" level.

4.3 Survey Data Analysis

With a small participant group, the quantitative survey data was analyzed through paired T-sample tests to avoid generalizing results across all survey responses, and each cycle's data was separately examined. Pre and post-surveys aimed to assess changes in comfort level, likelihood of using technology, and perceived relevance in the classroom.

In the first cycle with Technology Teachers, regarding comfort level with technology, no change was observed for both participants, who reported high comfort levels both before and after the intervention. Similarly, for the participants' likelihood of using these technologies with their students, MS and HS indicated consistent high likelihoods of using digital fabrication technologies on both the pre and the post survey.

Asking about teachers' perceptions of the relevance of this technology to their classroom learning revealed varying responses in cycle one. HS maintained a high perception of technology's relevance throughout, while MS noted a positive shift in perception post-intervention, acknowledging broader potential uses for students. Overall, despite the intervention, survey data indicated minimal changes in participants' confidence, likelihood of technology use, and perceived relevance.

For Subject Area Teachers in cycle two, I analyzed the quantitative survey data to explore Subject Area Teachers' comfort level, likelihood, and perceived relevance of the toolset. Both teachers showed increased confidence in using the technology, though initial levels varied. By the post-survey, both reported feeling "comfortable" using the technology, contrasting with cycle one where no increase was observed.

Regarding the likelihood of using the technology in their classrooms, both cycle two participants expressed a willingness to adopt the lesson plans incorporating the technology, indicating positive responses to integrating technology into their teaching practices. However, post-survey data showed mixed confidence levels in using the technology specifically with students in a classroom setting.

In examining the perception of technology relevance, KL noted an enhanced perception post-intervention, seeing broader applications for the technology in classroom lessons. The other participant's perception remained consistently high throughout, reflecting a robust existing perception of technology relevance in their teaching.

4.4 Qualitative Data Analysis

I analyzed participants' semi-structured interview transcripts and the field notes from lesson development sessions to explore comfort levels, perceived relevance, and likelihood of using technologies with students. Using inductive coding, I identified themes and categories in their verbal responses and comments, providing deeper insights beyond the quantitative survey data.

In cycle one, Technology Teachers did not show an increase in confidence when it came to using technologies with students, aligning with survey results. There was a notable theme emerging around the use of technologies with students, particularly observed in MS's case. While MS intended to incorporate a vinyl cutter into lessons, they expressed hesitation about deploying it with students, despite their familiarity with the technology.

In terms of likelihood to use these technologies, both participants expressed intentions to implement the developed lessons in the upcoming school year, aligning with survey results.

However, regarding the perception of technology relevance, a significant theme emerged from cycle one participants' interviews labeled "expanded learning opportunities." Despite both of the Technology Teachers' acknowledgement of the relevance of the digital fabrication equipment, their understanding evolved through our sessions. HS noted newfound applications for digital fabrication technologies, particularly in engaging girls in classes. MS saw the vinyl cutter as a catalyst for broader learning opportunities within their classroom and school, a shift in mindset towards the equipment's potential value. Both teachers discussed new found relevance, or expanded learning opportunities of the technology that they had been using already in their courses.

Cycle two participants showed increased confidence in technology through their experiences with the vinyl cutter, despite lacking prior exposure. They highlighted the significance of learning troubleshooting and software applications, which bolstered their confidence. However, their confidence in using the technology with students was less assured, reflecting a distinction noted in both qualitative and quantitative findings. MT expressed concerns about students' tech proficiency, while KL planned to incorporate the lesson plan cautiously, with adjustments if needed.

Despite varying confidence levels, both Subject Area Teachers intended to implement their lesson plans in the upcoming school year, underscoring their commitment despite reservations. MT demonstrated a heightened perception of technology relevance, envisioning broader applications beyond music, which aligned with the theme of "expanded learning opportunities" observed in cycle one.

In contrast to cycle one, where technology often overshadowed other learning goals, cycle two teachers integrated technology to enhance existing classroom objectives. They viewed technology as a novelty that could engage students more deeply in content learning, fostering excitement and making lessons more memorable. This theme of "student excitement" emerged prominently in their reflections, contrasting with cycle one participants who did not emphasize this aspect.

Overall, the qualitative data from both distinct cycles enriched understanding by revealing nuanced perspectives and thematic insights that complemented the survey findings.

5 Learnings and Implications

5.1 Reflections on Technology Teacher Outcomes

Cycle one involved two committed participants already familiar with using digital fabrication tools. These Technology Teachers plan to implement their lesson plans in the upcoming school year. Although the Technology Teachers did not show growth in their comfort level with the technology or their likelihood of using it with students, they experienced a shift in perception about its relevance in the classroom. This shift from technocentric to broader educational uses, particularly for MS, highlighted "expanded learning opportunities." This change may be attributed to the integration of pedagogy and research in the introduction session, the attention to TPACK during the intervention, and the emphasis on non-technocentric learning outcomes.

The discovery that not all in-service teachers use lesson planning regularly was unexpected with the Technology Teachers. I had assumed lesson planning would serve as an embedded practice; however, both Technology Teachers admitted to typically creating detailed instruction lists rather than comprehensive plans with learning objectives and standards in their daily practice. Reflecting on their experience of detailed lesson planning, HS remarked, "This is the first time I've ever done [such a complete] lesson plan," while MS acknowledged the value of the template in prompting deeper reflection: "I think the [lesson plan] template certainly served its purpose in terms of getting me to really think through this."

Another theme, "technocentric student learning," emerged from the Technology Teacher interviews and field notes and was supported in the literature. Cycle one participants focused their discussions heavily on machines, software, and projects, often emphasizing technocentric outcomes over expanded learning opportunities when discussing lesson plans.

Cycle one teachers exhibited a tendency to prioritize "focus on the project, not the learning," as evidenced by their emphasis on final project outcomes rather than student learning goals during lesson planning. This approach, noted in field notes and interviews, revealed their strategy of starting with the project and then considering its educational rationale. One participant's goal exemplified this focus: "I want them to design a plastic package for a mini skateboard."

An interesting takeaway from cycle one was that the one-to-one lesson development sessions were beneficial not due to embedded practice but because of the community support aspect. Developing

lessons together allowed participants to lean into a professional learning community, even a small community of two. This theme of "peer support in planning," was highlighted by both teachers. MS noted, "Just having someone to bounce ideas off of and help shape [the lesson plan]" was valuable. Neither teacher typically engages in shared lesson planning, making this collaborative process particularly impactful. This theme underscores the importance, identified in research, of teachers integrating technology best through professional learning communities. The intervention unintentionally fostered this community aspect, demonstrating how even a small group can support teachers in integrating digital fabrication technology. Additionally, participants MS and HS found the final virtual session, where they presented and discussed their lesson plans, to be especially helpful, as noted in their interviews.

5.2 Reflections on Subject Area Teacher Outcomes

The second cycle occurred at the start of the school year, another busy time for teachers. Both participants were Subject Area Teachers with little prior experience in this technology. Despite this, they plan to implement the developed lesson plans with their students. This positive outcome suggests the intervention was effective in showcasing the toolset's potential. However, there might be a selection bias among participating teachers, possibly influenced by the offer of a vinyl cutter for their classrooms. This may help explain the high interest.

These teachers joined with a keen interest in the technology despite starting with limited experience. Unlike cycle one, this cycle focused substantially on enhancing their technological skills within the TPACK framework. They dedicated 50% to 60% (two to three hours) of the intervention to learning how to use the technology, which directly contributed to their increased confidence in it.

The contrast in outcomes between cycle one and cycle two participants was evident in the completion status of their final lesson plans. While Subject Area Teachers confirmed that they practice weekly lesson planning, unlike Technology Teachers, their lesson plan templates remained somewhat incomplete. Neither participant continued working on their plans independently post-intervention, possibly due to the absence of a scheduled presentation session.

An unexpected discovery from cycle two was the emphasis on the novelty of the technology itself, a theme not initially anticipated from the literature review. This "student excitement" theme could stem from selection bias or the comparative inexperience of cycle two teachers compared to the Technology Teachers.

5.3 Contributing Domain to the Problem Statement

The Ishikawa diagram developed through empathy interviews, research, and professional experience highlighted factors like "time and space, technology knowledge, pedagogy and integration knowledge, standardized testing, and support network." During analysis, a new factor emerged: students' technological literacy. MT expressed concern about teaching both "the tech end as well as the music end." This concern was shared by both tech ed teachers in cycle one, who emphasized the importance of the learning sequence for technology skills. For instance, HS planned their lesson after students had learned CAD and 2D design. Originally categorized under "technocentric student learning," a nuanced understanding showed the importance of technological literacy in teaching content. Subject area teachers lacked the freedom tech ed teachers had to prepare students, highlighting a gap in preparedness. Pitkänen et al. (2019) noted the challenge of "scaffolding for student learning" in makerspace activities. My findings align with this, emphasizing the need for foundational technology instruction before lessons. Thus, I would update the fishbone diagram to include "student preparedness" as a contributing domain. Reflected in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Additional Contributing Domain

Note. This "bone" is an additional domain to be added to the original Ishikawa diagram in Figure 1 describing the additional problem area of "student preparedness." Own work.

5.4 Embedded Practice

The change idea for this intervention, "work one to one with teachers to develop lesson plans in support of class curriculum," is shown in the driver diagram. This idea stemmed from the research theme of "classroom and embedded practice," for professional learning with technology. The study challenged the assumption that lesson development is a daily practice for teachers, with only half indicating they use it weekly. The virtual lesson plan development sessions did not reflect the embedded practice theme as assumed. For Technology Teachers, this was unique because they usually do not write lesson plans, while for Subject Area Teachers, it was novel to collaborate. The sessions were not embedded practice as expected.

5.5 Professional Learning Community

The review highlighted the importance of professional learning communities (PLCs) in integrating new technologies in teaching. While initially planned as a shared lesson plan presentation, only cycle one teachers experienced this session positively, interacting and learning from each other. Cycle two lacked this opportunity, yet both groups expressed benefit from collaborative lesson development sessions, where my role shifted from an expert to a collaborator, forming a small community of practice.

5.6 Digital Making in all Classrooms

A relevant analogy to the development timeline of digital makerspaces in education is the journey of computers into formal classrooms. As Bull et al. (2010) stated, we can "anticipate a number of parallels between the advent of personal computing and the advent of personal fabrication" (p.5). When computers were first introduced into schools, they were installed in a computer lab where a computer teacher taught the students how to use this technology. Even Papert's Logo programming language, as foundational as it was to constructionism, began by engaging the students in technical content through programming (Papert, 1980). Today, though, computers are present in many classrooms and not confined to a computer lab anymore. Students learn with computers in history, math, art, and even foreign language classes. If digital fabrication technologies are following a parallel track, schools are currently in the "computer lab" phase in which the makerspace technologies are confined to one room where often students go to learn the technologies themselves. We need to prepare our teachers for the next step of

the timeline, where the machines move into various classes and are used differently in education. 3D printers, vinyl cutters, and laser cutters are tools that can be used to teach any content.

This study was designed to investigate how teachers can integrate these tools into lessons that meet classroom learning objectives. For the participating teachers, these included technological learning objectives, music concepts, and library lessons. Even though I had only a small sample of teachers, I posit that every classroom can benefit from digital making integration in respect to subject area content. With proper attention to the root causes on the fishbone diagram: student preparedness, time and space, TPACK knowledge domains, support networks, and standardized curriculum, every teacher should be able to use these technologies to reach their students with a hands-on approach to the content.

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Elizabeth Whitewolf: Activating Fab Labs for Classroom Learning: Supporting K-12 teachers in technology integration

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Elizabeth Whitewolf: Activating Fab Labs for Classroom Learning: Supporting K-12 teachers in technology integration

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